

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 53

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 53

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 53:1 "The fool has said in his heart, "There is no God," They are corrupt, and have committed abominable injustice; ^bThere is no one who does good. ² God has looked down from heaven upon the sons of men To see if there is "anyone who ¹understands, Who ^bseeks after God. ³ "Every one of them has turned aside; together they have become corrupt; There is no one who does good, not even one.</p> <p>Psa. 53:4 Have the workers of wickedness "no knowledge, Who eat up My people <i>as though</i> they ate bread And have not called upon God? ⁵ There they were in great ¹fear <i>where</i> no ¹fear had been; For God ^bscattered the bones of ²him who encamped against you; You ^cput <i>them</i> to shame, because ^dGod had rejected them. ⁶ Oh, that ^athe salvation of Israel ¹would come out of Zion! When God ²restores His captive people, ³Let Jacob rejoice, let Israel be glad.</p>	<p>Psa. 53:1 לְמִנְצַחַת עַל-מַחְלַת מִשְׁכִּיל לְדָוִד : ² אָמַר נָבֵל בְּלִבּוֹ אֵין אֱלֹהִים הִשְׁחִיתוּ וְהִתְעִיבוּ עוֹל אֵין עֲשֵׂה-טוֹב : ³ אֱלֹהִים מִשְׁמַיִם הִשְׁקִיף עַל-בְּנֵי אָדָם לְרֹאוֹת הַיֵּשׁ מִשְׁכִּיל הֲיֵשׁ אֶת-אֱלֹהִים : ⁴ כָּלוּ סִגְיֹתָם וְנִאֲלְחוּ אֵין עֲשֵׂה-טוֹב אֵין גַּם-אֶחָד : ⁵ הֲלֹא יָדְעוּ פִּעְלֵי אֱוֹן אֲכָלִי עַמִּי אָכְלוּ לֶחֶם אֱלֹהִים לֹא קָרְאוּ : ⁶ נֶשֶׁם אִפְתָּרוּ-פֶּתַח לֹא- הָיָה פֶּתַח כִּי-אֱלֹהִים פִּזֹּר עֲצָמוֹת חֲנֹךְ הִבְשֵׁתָה כִּי-אֱלֹהִים מְאֹסִים : ⁷ מִי יִתֵּן מִצִּיּוֹן יִשְׁעוֹת יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּשׁוּב אֱלֹהִים שְׁבוֹת עַמּוֹ יִגַּל יַעֲקֹב יִשְׂמַח יִשְׂרָאֵל :</p>

References

Psalm 53:0

I.e. sickness, a sad tone

¹Possibly *Contemplative*, or *Didactic*, or *Skillful Psalm*

Psalm 53:1

^aPs 10:4; 14:1-7; 53:1-6

^bRom 3:10

Psalm 53:2

¹Or *acts wisely*

^aRom 3:11

^b2 Chr 15:2

Psalm 53:3

^aRom 3:12

Psalm 53:4

^aJer 4:22

Psalm 53:5

¹Or *dread*

²Or possibly *those*

^aLev 26:17, 36; Prov 28:1

^bPs 141:7; Jer 8:1, 2; Ezek 6:5

^cPs 44:7

^d2 Kin 17:20; Jer 6:30; Lam 5:22

Psalm 53:6

¹Lit *would be*

²Or *restores the fortunes of His people*

³Or *Jacob will rejoice, Israel will be glad*

^aPs 14:7**Targum**

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses are in bold.

Introduction

Psalm 53 is an almost exact replica of Psalm 14. Psalm 14 is believed to be about the destruction of the first Temple, while Psalm 53 is about the destruction of the second Temple. Since David wrote this Psalm, it was a prediction that David made. Since it came to pass, this proves that David had prophetic gifts from the LORD.

The establishment of the House of David was not an easy task. Besides Saul and his family trying to stop David, several nations surrounding Israel did not want it to happen. Saul was weak in foreign policy, and David was viewed as being strong. The LORD established David on the throne of Israel, and his descendants were to be on the throne until the day of the Messiah. On that day, any exile of the Jewish people would terminate. However, the Psalm says that the Messiah will suffer persecution at the hands of skeptics and scoffers.

This is a problem for Jews to accept Jesus of Nazareth as more than a prophet. The traditions outlined in this Psalm and in other writings indicate the vindication of Israel with an end to foreign rule, just to mention one item. This did not happen when Jesus of Nazareth was born. Jesus was born in Galilee. That places doubts on his being a part of the line of David. Jews in Judea at that time did not view Galileans nor Samaritans as Jews.

Superscript

מַהֲלַת (Mahalat) - “This technical musical term of uncertain meaning is found in the headings of Ps 53 and 88 [H 53:1 and 88:1]. Most [Vol. 1, p. 288] versions transliterate the term. The NASB suggests a connection with הָלַח “to be weak, sick,” hence a sad tune. Others relate it to מְחֻלָּה, a round dance. In Ps 88, where it is joined with “Leannoth,” the NIV says it may possibly be a tune, “The Suffering of Affliction.” For other such terms see סִלְהָ.”¹

נִצְחָה (Natacha) – this word is the name of the Sefirah Netzach. This Sefirah offers victory to the people who call upon its name.

To Netzach who grants victory over widespread infirmity, an instruction by David.

Verse 1

Psalm 14 voiced a faith that has sustained Israel since its inception. This faith has kept the Hebrew people together throughout its long period of destitution.

נָבַל (naval) verb, be senseless, foolish. It can also be translated as "withered." History has shown that humans enter a time of mental and moral degradation whenever they become foolish.

Israel's enemies called them foolish for their faith and hope in the LORD. As long as Israel kept their covenant with the LORD, they were always protected. נָבַל denotes

¹ R. Laird Harris, Gleason L. Archer, and Bruce K. Waltke, “Theological Wordbook of The Old Testament (1980 Edition),” Open Library (Moody Press, January 1, 1980), https://openlibrary.org/books/OL4112955M/Theological_wordbook_of_the_Old_Testament.

the disappearance of unfettered moral strength. The nation was "going down the tubes," and it appeared that no one could stop it.

In his heart, the foolish man has said, "There is no God"; they are corrupt and an abomination because their activities are not those of a person who wants to do good.

Verse 2

Humans who deny the existence of the LORD do so because the LORD cannot be detected by reason.

The LORD observes from Heaven to find humans who are searching for Him by using their reason.

Verse 3

The author believed that every person was corrupt and had turned away from the LORD. Therefore, the LORD does not need to intervene and bring punishment to the people because every member of society serves as a punishment for his/her fellow citizens. In other words, the people punish each other by their violence toward each other.

There have often been periods when all humanity seemed to be corrupted, and no one did anything good.

All humanity is depraved. No one is doing anything good, not a single person.

Verse 4

Even when it appears that all humanity is corrupt and perverted, there has always been a nation that respected the LORD and obeyed His divine law. That nation is Israel. Without Israel, the world would have become completely lost.

The doers of violence do not know who devours Israel like a person eating bread and has not invited the LORD?

Verse 5

The people who transgressed against the people of Israel learned about divine justice.

There they were in great fear where no fear had been; For God scattered the bones of him who encamped against you; You put them to shame, because God had rejected them.

Verse 6

Salvation is a gift given to Israel by the LORD.

Oh, that the salvation of Israel would come out of Zion! When God restores His captive people, Let Jacob rejoice, let Israel be glad.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Netzach who grants victory over widespread infirmity, an instruction by David.

In his heart, the foolish man has said, "There is no God"; they are corrupt and an abomination because their activities are not those of a person who wants to do good.

The LORD observes from Heaven to find humans who are searching for Him by using their reason.

All humanity is depraved. No one is doing anything good, not a single person.

The doers of violence do not know who devours Israel like a person eating bread and has not invited the LORD?

There they were in great fear where no fear had been; For God scattered the bones of him who encamped against you; You put them to shame, because God had rejected them.

Oh, that the salvation of Israel would come out of Zion! When God restores His captive people, Let Jacob rejoice, let Israel be glad.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

